

Emergent spatial patterns can indicate upcoming regime shifts in a realistic model of coral community - Supplement 4: Indicator trends for all parameter combinations

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This appendix contains extended version of figures 3, 4 and 5 (in the main text) with all parameter combinations (*i.e.* including $d_0 = 0.5$).

Figure S4.1 Algae, bare and coral covers at equilibrium (bottom panels) and indicator values (upper panels) along an increase in coral baseline mortality (m_c), for different types of coral local feedback d_0 , and indicators computed either on the cover of coral (red) or algae (blue). Dotted lines in indicator trends (a-d1, 2, 3) indicate non-significant trends (correlation test, $P > 0.01$). The black vertical line indicates the point up to which indicator trends are considered.

Figure S4.2 Algae, bare and coral covers at equilibrium (bottom panels) and indicator values (upper panels) along a decrease in herbivore pressure (h_w), for different types of coral local feedback d_0 , and indicators computed either on the cover of coral (red) or algae (blue). Dotted lines in indicator trends indicate non-significant trends (correlation test, $P > 0.01$). The black vertical line indicates the point up to which indicator trends are considered.

Figure S4.3 Average cover of algae, bare and coral covers (bottom panels) and indicator values (upper panels) along an increase in return time of mortality events ($\Delta I(52 p_e)$), for different types of local coral feedback d_0 , and indicators computed either on the cover of coral (red) or algae (blue). Dotted lines in indicator trends indicate non-significant trends (correlation test, $P > 0.01$). The black vertical line indicates the point up to which indicator trends are considered.